

D6.8 Report on the One Health EJP Summer School (Y3)

WP6: Education and Training

Responsible Partner: UoS (P23)

GENERAL INFORMATION

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Local Organising Committee	Wim van der Poel, Marianne Bruining, Henk Hogeveen, Huub Zonjee, Paddy Haripersau
Collaborating Organising Institutes	Wageningen Institute of Animal Sciences, the Netherlands University of Surrey (UoS), UK Netherlands Centre for One Health (NCOH), the Netherlands Institut national de la recherche agronomique (INRA), France Agreenium, France
Collaborating Organisers	Professor Roberto La Ragione, Dr Piyali Basu, Dr Jade Passey, Elaine Campling, Dr Dan Horton, Annemarie Rebel, Aurelie Binot, Marianne Bruining.

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Introduction

The One Health Summer School focuses on the One Health concept, which recognises that human health is tightly connected to animals and the environment. Multiple reports have highlighted the need for 'One Health' interventions towards the delivery of better health outcomes across each of the health domains. Therefore, One Health actions must contribute value over and above the status-quo traditionally characterised by isolated or domain-specific approaches.

The aim of this Summer School was to learn how to understand and operationalise a "Global One Health" approach to improve the health of humans, animals, and the environment within a sustainable ecosystem.

This Summer School was organised by the Local Organising team at Wageningen BioVeterinary Research (WBVR) institute in the Netherlands and led by Professor Wim van der Poel, in collaboration with Wageningen Institute of Animal Sciences, Netherlands Centre for One Health, Institut national de la recherche agronomique (INRA), Agreenium, and finally the One Health EJP Work Package 6 team and Communications team based at the University of Surrey.

The event was originally planned as a face-to-face event; however, the COVID-19 pandemic brought many challenges, the largest ones being the impact on global travel and the safety of all those who attend. The programme was adapted so it could be delivered online and was still of high-quality. It is worth mentioning that the Summer School had to be re-organised within a short timescale, and at a time when WBVR was heavily involved in COVID-19 research.

Organising a two-week event online brought its own additional challenges. It was critical to ensure a secure and stable hosting internet connection, which was provided by the Wageningen University. Delegates, lecturers, chairs and organisers were all located in individual locations across the world, and the quality of every person's internet connection and bandwidth varies; this is ultimately out of one's control; however, the organisers provided the option to have their cameras off to reduce the bandwidth required. There were some early inevitable technical challenges associated with a platform new to most attendees, however these were quickly overcome.

The task of keeping the attention of 34 delegates' and make them feel involved and motivated by the discussions through a screen for 6-7 hours each day over two weeks is no easy task. The lecturers organised online individual and group exercises and

discussions on the platform and used several different online tools for the programme to be interactive and engaging.

The physical Summer School planned to have two social events with the aim of nurturing and building on the relationships formed in an informal setting. Instead, a 'virtual drinks' session was hosted by one of the lecturers who is also on the local organising team, and this was an opportunity at the end of the first day to allow the group to get to know more about each other and socialise and to nurture the relationships which were to be formed in the coming weeks. These delegates now belong to the One Health EJP alumni, and have since, attended other OHEJP events.

The organising team overcame all these challenges, and the programme still covered a wide variety of One Health topics (see [programme structure](#) for more info), and the human, animal and environment areas were well represented, as were the perspectives from governance, politics, social sciences and ethics. The successes of the Summer School were evident from the collaborative discussions that took place, the knowledge and experiences shared, and the collaborative engagements and future relationships formed between 34 participants across 20 countries. The written [testimonials](#) from our delegates provide the evidence for this.

Theme

The Global One Health (GOH) concept emphasises the interdependence of human health with the health of animals, plants and sustainable ecosystems from a global perspective. True prosperity and security will only be reached if we weigh all possible effects of interventions on the health of humans, animals, plants and the environment, while taking ecosystem sustainability into account.

The GOH approach uses multiple disciplines to seek transnational solutions for improving the health of humans, animals and plants, and ultimately, the sustainability of the ecosystems of planet earth.

Aims and Objectives

The aim of this Summer School was to understand and learn how to operationalise a Global One Health approach to improve the health of people, animals and plants within a sustainable ecosystem.

The Summer School aimed to provide :

- An understanding of the complexity of health challenges and how to apply the Global One health concept to address these.

- Ways to identify, characterize and quantify the drivers of value from Global One Health approaches across research and programmatic areas (e.g. prediction, detection) and stakeholders.
- An ability to recognize GOH research methods and operationalize these for effective preparedness and response to Global One Health threats.
- An understanding of the application of robust monitoring and evaluation tools to implement Global One Health interventions.

Speakers

A list of all the speakers and their organisations or institutes can be found in the programme, and the bios and photos of these speakers can be found on the [Summer School web-page](#) on the OHEJP website. Speakers were from different important institutes and organisations within the Global One Health arena. Speakers were from the medical as well as the veterinary field and also from environmental sciences. This has resulted in a true Global One Health coverage on research as well as policy.

Programme Structure

This year's programme followed on from last year's Summer School and boasted leading EU and international experts in public health, animal health and environmental health who face today's challenges to implement One Health strategies in the different health fields.

The programme was delivered by the experts on the Brightspace Learning Environment platform (see [logistical arrangements](#) for further details). Experts provided pre-reading materials consisting of relevant research papers and articles for delegates to read before the course. These were emailed by the local organising team.

The programme consisted of lectures and interactive activities and exercises to deliver an introduction to Global One Health basics, prediction approaches, analyses of integrated disease surveillance, outcomes research, risk management, and decision quality. The programme was between 6 and 7.5 hours each day, with lunch breaks and coffee breaks, and was split into topical sessions which were chaired by one or more lecturers. To see the programme, see [annex 3](#).

Delegates had the opportunity to present their own experiences and ideas in the Global One Health field which was subsequently discussed with lecturers and participants of the course. Delegates also participated in a number of other activities including a Q&A sessions with an expert from the Food and Agriculture Organisation, group breakout session led by an expert from the World Health Organisation, an interactive critical review of scientific papers and two assignments including a zoonoses modelling assignment.

A wide variety of One Health topics were covered including: disease surveillance for One Health, wildlife and public health, zoonoses modelling, AMR in animals, human and the environment, air- risk of aerosols, droplets and dust, soil- risk from manure-borne diseases, and parasites in the food chain amongst other topics. The programme also included other factors to consider during implementation of One Health strategies such as governance and politics of One Health, sustainable development, economics in global health, socioeconomic impact emerging zoonoses, and connecting with stakeholders.

Delegates had plenty of opportunities during and after the Summer School to follow up with lecturers to seek relevant resources and advice. The pre-reading materials, and all course materials (with permission) remained on the virtual platform whilst individual user accounts remained active for 2 months for delegates to access after the event.

The school was promoted not only as a learning opportunity, but also a very important networking opportunity. The virtual drinks social event took place at the end of the first day, and provided an opportunity to encourage introductions, networking and collaborative discussions amongst delegates and lecturers in a more informal setting (see [photos](#)).

Logistical arrangements

The Summer School 2020 was originally planned as a physical event, to take place in the Netherlands from 17th to 28th August, with pre-reading tasks set prior to the course. The programme was designed for a face-to-face event, and speakers were invited to teach and deliver one or more sessions at the Summer School. This planning and invitation process took place between October 2019 and February 2020. In March 2020, the COVID-19 pandemic and the uncertainty it brought significantly impacted the logistical planning and milestones to organise a physical event. With global travel impacted, Work Package 6 and the local organisers discussed the challenges and agreed on the solution of delivering this event in a virtual format, so that the education and training of the students, researchers and other related professionals can still take place despite the ongoing pandemic.

Following this decision, the programme structure was modified so that the training could be delivered successfully online on the original dates intended. The hosting connection for this event was at Wageningen University, and was delivered using the Brightspace Learning Environment platform, which is a learning management system used by the university for creating, hosting, editing online learning resources and teaching lectures to their students. The materials and meeting links were organised into days and then further sub-categorised into sessions. All delegates had a user account setup with Wageningen University to access the Summer School on the Brightspace platform. Instructions to join the different sessions and access materials for each day were communicated prior to the event clearly to delegates and lecturers. A contact for technical support was available prior to and throughout the entire event.

For more details on the programme, please refer to [Programme structure](#).

During the event, the One Health EJP Communications Team shared screenshots of the event on social media in real-time. Permission was obtained prior to the event during the registration process from all delegates and lecturers.

At the end of the programme, feedback evaluation forms were collected from delegates. The evaluations were shared between the local organisers, WP6 team and OHEJP communications team. The WP6 team updated the protocol created for Local Event Organisers with the lessons learned from this event, and more specifically, specific guidance for organisation of virtual events, to ensure the feedback is implemented in future WP6 events. The feedback forms also captured testimonials from delegates, and the communications team created branded visual montages from screenshots and testimonials captured. These montages were used to report and share the successes of the Summer School through a [blog post](#), on the One Health EJP website, social media channels, and the One Health EJP newsletters and bulletins.

Promotional Campaign

The promotional campaign was managed by the One Health EJP Communications Team and began at the start of June 2020, with a [‘Save the Date’ promotional flyer](#), which communicated the theme of the Summer School, dates, location (online) and target audience. This first flyer was disseminated through the internal OHEJP communication channels (monthly education and training activities bulletin) and external OHEJP communication channels (OHEJP website, social media, One Health Commission social media channels).

A dedicated web-page was created for the One Health EJP Summer School 2020 in June 2020 which initially described when, where and how much it costs to attend the Summer School, along with the save the date flyer, aims of the Summer School and eligibility rules.

A second [full event flyer](#) was created to provide more detailed information about the concept and theme of the Summer School, the aims and objectives, target audience. It also provided a link to the application form created by the communications team to attend the Summer School, along with the deadline. This was disseminated through the same internal and external channels described for the save the date flyer.

As the speakers were confirmed for the final programme, they were asked to provide short biographies and a headshot photo. These were added to the website page as they were received leading up to the event, and the announcement of these speakers for the Summer School was also shared on social media to increase awareness of the event and traffic to the OHEJP website. Please note, many speaker biographies and photos were

published before the full event flyer was published and the application process was opened to encourage the submission of applications.

The communications team created branded visual montages from the screenshots and testimonials captured. These montages were used to report and share the successes of the Summer School through a [blog post](#), on the [One Health EJP Summer School 2020 webpage](#). This was shared through the One Health EJP social media channels- [Twitter](#) and [LinkedIn](#), and the following [monthly education and training activities bulletins](#) and [OHEJP newsletters](#) published in 2020.

Applications and selection procedure

In total, 63 applications were received from 28 countries across the world. The 63 applicants for the Summer School were from a range of educational backgrounds (see figure below). This was considered during the selection process to ensure that there was enough diversity of interdisciplinary backgrounds because it would bring many different One Health perspectives and initiate collaborative discussions. In the end, this significantly contributed to the success of the Summer School.

Applicants also had a range of educational levels (see figure below), which was once again an important consideration because the Summer School aims to train the future One Health scientists. It was important to have a range of educational levels to stimulate discussions and collaborations between the delegates but also so that those at undergraduate level could learn from their peers with more experience.

The 63 applications were screened using the selection criteria below by the local organizing team, and then checked for gender balance. 34 delegates were selected. As the event was virtual, the decision was made to accommodate up to an additional 15 participants compared to last year without compromising the quality of the interactions.

- Consortium members vs. Non- Consortium members
- Experience
- Educational background
- Highest Education Level
- Area of expertise

Delegates

The Summer School hosted 34 delegates from 20 countries and from the institutes listed below. As you will see, one of the delegates selected was from European Food Safety Authority, one of the OHEJP's stakeholders.

The delegates belonged to a range of education levels and interdisciplinary backgrounds as described above, which brought a diverse pool of experience and knowledge in One Health to provide this opportunity of these unique multi-disciplinary and collaborative interactions.

(* OHEJP Consortium Member; ** OHEJP Stakeholder)

1. France
 - a. Universite de Tours
2. Spain
 - a. VISAVET Health Surveillance Centre-UCM*
 - b. Universidad CEU Cardenal Herrera
 - c. Universidad Peruana de Ciencias Aplicadas
3. United Kingdom
 - a. University of Edinburgh
 - b. The Animal and Plant Health Agency*
 - c. University of Surrey (School of Veterinary Medicine) *
4. Romania
 - a. University of Agricultural Sciences and Veterinary Medicine Cluj-Napoc
5. Denmark
 - a. Roskilde University
6. Lithuania
 - a. Lithuanian University of Health Sciences (Veterinary Academy)
7. Portugal
 - a. Centre for Ecology, Evolution and Environmental Changes (cE3c)
 - b. National Institute for Agrarian and Veterinarian Research (INIAV) *
 - c. University of Évora
 - d. University of Lisbon
 - e. Hospital de São João
8. Germany
 - a. Bundesinstitut für Risikobewertung (BfR) *
 - b. Vétérinaires Sans Frontières Germany (VSFG)
9. Ghana
 - a. Council for Scientific and Industrial Research
10. India
 - a. Ashoka Trust for Research in Ecology and Environment
11. The Netherlands
 - a. Dutch National Institute for Public Health and Environment (RIVM)*
 - b. Amsterdam UMC
12. Italy
 - a. European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) **
 - b. Sapienza Università di Roma
 - c. Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale del Mezzogiorno
13. Nigeria

- a. Department of Community Health National postgraduate medical college of Nigeria
- 14. Ukraine
 - a. National Pirogov Memorial Medical University
- 15. Belgium
 - a. University of Liège
 - b. Institute of Tropical Medicine
- 16. China
 - a. China Agricultural University
- 17. Nepal
 - a. Agriculture and Forestry University
- 18. Phillipines
 - a. University of the Philippines
- 19. Finland
 - a. Resistomap Oy
- 20. Dominic Republic of Congo
 - a. Kinshasa School of Public Health

Certificates of Attendance

A branded OHEJP Certificate of Attendance template was created by the One Health EJP Communications Team. The local organisers recorded attendance of all delegates and used the template to distribute certificates to each participant one week after the event.

Testimonials

The testimonials were captured in the feedback evaluation forms collected from delegates, and from the 'chat' facility on the online platform used. Permission to publish these testimonials was obtained during the registration process.

Lead Organiser Testimonial

Professor Wim van der Poel, Wageningen BioVeterinary institute- 'We look back on a very successful Global One Health Summer school. The programme was pretty full, but delegates were really happy with all the presentations. The organisers in Wageningen were very pleased about the excellent inputs of the delegates. This was organised in interactive discussion groups and by presentations of the delegates of their own Global One Health activities. Very interesting to hear and very good exchange! This will for sure help delegates with their future activities in the Global One Health field.'

Delegate Testimonials

Please see the testimonials from our delegates below.

Two of the One Health EJP PhD students who attended the Summer School wrote longer testimonials which can be found on the [blog post](#).

Photos

Written permission was obtained from all those in any photographs taken. This was done during the registration/application process. The montage below was created by the OHEJP communications team.

Blog post

Work Package 6 worked closely with the One Health EJP Communications Team to create a blog post to promote the successes of the event, publish photos and testimonials. The published blog post can be found on the One Health EJP website [here](#).

This blog post was promoted in the Education and Training activities monthly bulletins, OHEJP newsletters and through the official OHEJP social media channels.

Internal Events Survey information

The European Commission requires all dissemination and communication activities, and events to be reported. **Please complete both the [Internal Events Survey](#) and the table below as accurately as possible.**

Name of the activity:	One Health EJP Summer School 2020		
Date:	17 th – 28 th August 2020		
Place:	Online event (Brightspace)		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	No	Participation to a Conference	No
Organisation of a Workshop	Yes	Participation to a Workshop	No
Press release	No	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	No
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)	No	Video/Film	No
Exhibition	No	Brokerage Event	No
Flyer	Yes	Pitch Event	No
Training	Yes	Trade Fair	No
Social Media	Yes	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	No
Website	Yes	Other	No
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	No		
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	65	Media	0
Industry	0	Investors	0
Civil Society	0	Customers	0
General Public	0	Other	0
Policy Makers *EFSA Stakeholder	1		

Annex 1: "Save the Date" Promotional Flyer

Save the Date!
One Health EJP Summer School 2020
Global One Health - From Research to Practice

Date:

17th to 28th August 2020

Location:

This event will now be a virtual event.
More information coming soon

Audience:

PhD students and Bachelor's, Masters, researchers with some experience in a health related field.

#OneHealthEJP #OHEJPSummerSchool2020

Annex 2: Summer School full Promotional Flyer

Save the Date!
One Health EJP Summer School 2020
Global One Health - From Research to Practice

Date:

17th to 28th August 2020

Location:

This will be a virtual event with a €100 registration fee

Audience:

PhD students and Bachelor's, Masters, researchers with some experience in a health related field.

 @OneHealthEJP

 ONE Health EJP

#OneHealthEJP #OHEJPSummerSchool2020

The Global One Health concept

The Global One Health (GOH) concept emphasizes the interdependence of human health with the health of animals, plants and sustainable ecosystems from a global perspective. True prosperity and security will only be reached if we weigh all possible effects of interventions on the health of humans, animals, plants and the environment, while taking ecosystem sustainability into account. The GOH approach uses multiple disciplines to seek transnational solutions for improving the health of humans, animals and plants, and ultimately, the sustainability of the ecosystems of planet earth.

The aim of the Summer School will be to understand and learn how to operationalise a Global One Health approach to improve the health people animals and plants within a sustainable ecosystem.

This Summer School aims to provide:

- an understanding of the complexity of health challenges and how to apply the Global One health concept to address these.
- ways to identify, characterize and quantify the drivers of value from Global One Health approaches across research and programmatic areas (e.g. prediction, detection) and stakeholders
- an ability to recognize GOH research methods and operationalize these for effective preparedness and response to Global One Health threats
- an understanding of the application of robust monitoring and evaluation tools to implement Global One Health interventions.

Participants:

Students will learn a number of technical and organisational approaches of which the practicalities will be further explained and can be discussed in the interdisciplinary parts of the course. The programme will deliver an introduction to Global One Health basics, prediction approaches, analyses of integrated disease surveillance, outcomes research, risk management, and decision quality. In this online course students will have the opportunity to present their own experiences and ideas in the Global One Health field which subsequently can be discussed with lecturers and participants of the course.

Registration closes at midnight on 31 July 2020 CEST: [registration form](#)

Annex 3: Summer School Programme

One Health EJP Summer School 2020 Global One Health - From Research to Practice

Monday 17th August Topic Chair: Wim van der Poel

9 - 10 am CEST	Introduction to Global One Health: Wim van der Poel, Wageningen University
10 - 11 am	From signal to decision: a One Health structure to facilitate policy making: Hendrik Jan Roest, Wageningen University
1 - 2 pm	Emerging Infectious diseases and zoonoses: Wim van der Poel, Wageningen University
2 - 3 pm	Case studies illustrating a one health approach to emerging viral infections: Daniel Horton, University of Surrey
3:30 - 4:30 pm	Virtual get together with drinks

Tuesday 18th August Topic Chair: Victor Del Rio Vilas, Wim van der Poel

9 - 10 am	Global Health: Victor Del Rio Vilas, WHO
10 - 11 am	Q&A: Katinka de Balogh, FAO
11 - 12 am	Break-out session: Gyanendra Gongal, WHO
1 - 2 pm	Control of infectious diseases in the tropics: Michelle van Vugt, Academic Medical Centre Amsterdam
2 - 3 pm	Control of infectious diseases in the tropics: Sander Koenraadt, Wageningen University

Wednesday 19th August Topic Chair: Daniel Horton

9 - 10 am	Disease surveillance for One Health: Katrin Kuhn (tbc),
10 - 11 am	Disease surveillance for One Health: Ruth Bouwstra, Royal GD
1 - 2 pm	Participant presentation
2 - 3 pm	Spatial Analysis for Integrated Surveillance (SAIS) of One Health: Andrew Lawson, Medical University, South Carolina
3.30 - 4.30 pm	Assignment Zoonoses modelling: Andrew Lawson, Medical University, South Carolina <i>Paper assignment will be circulated beforehand</i>

Thursday 20th August Topic Chair: Roberto La Ragione, Ines Kuniko Mogami Gonzale

9 - 10 am	AMR in animals, humans and the environment; a One Health issue: Roberto La Ragione, University of Surrey
10 - 11 am	Implementing the One Health concept to combat AMR in the Netherlands: Kees Veldman, Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
11 - 12 am	Interactive critical review of scientific papers
1 - 2 pm	Governance and politics of One Health: Ines Kuniko Mogami Gonzalez, RIVM
2 - 3 pm	Governance and politics of One Health: Henk-Jan Ormel, FAO

Friday 21st August Topic Chair: Henk Hogeveen

am	Sustainable food systems/ Food security: <i>Lecturer to be recruited</i>
pm	Economics in Global One Health: Henk Hogeveen, Wageningen University

One Health EJP Summer School 2020 Global One Health - From Research to Practice

Monday 24th August Topic Chair: Ana Maria de Roda Husman, Ron Bergevoet

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| 9 - 10 am CEST | Water - from wastewater as a surveillance tool to waterborne infectious disease risk: Ana Maria de Roda Husman, RIVM |
| 10 - 11 am | Air - risk from aerosols, droplets, dust: Lucie Vermeulen, RIVM |
| 11 - 12 pm | Soil - risk from manure borne zoonoses: Sophia Dollmann, RIVM |
| 2 - 3 pm | Socio-economic impact of (emerging) zoonosis: Taking economic and social sciences into account during decision making: Ron Bergevoet, WeCR |
| 3 - 4 pm | Parasites in the food chain: global one health risks: Joke van der Giessen, RIVM |

Tuesday 25th August Topic Chair: Hein Imberechts, Mart de Jong

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|------------|---|
| 9 - 10 am | The One Health EJP and its successful relationship with its stakeholders: Hein Imberechts, Sciensano |
| 10 - 11 am | Connecting with stakeholders: Annemarie Kaesbohrer, Bfr Berlin |
| 1 - 2 pm | Connecting data analysis and modelling: Estimating parameters for infection dynamics: Mart de Jong, Wageningen University |
| 2 - 3 pm | Connecting data analysis and modelling: Estimating parameters for infection dynamics: Mart de Jong, Wageningen University |

Wednesday 26th August Topic Chair: Anabelle Daburon, Marcel Verweij

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| 9 - 10 am | Sustainable development: Anabelle Daburon, Wageningen University |
| 10 - 11 am | Sustainable development: Anabelle Daburon, Wageningen University |
| 1 - 2 pm | Ethics of One Health: Marcel Verweij, Wageningen University |
| 2 - 3 pm | Ethics of One Health: Marcel Verweij, Wageningen University |
| 3.30 - 4.30 pm | Discussion and assignment |

Thursday 27th August Topic Chair: Evelien de Olde (afternoon)

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| 9 - 10 am | Risk assessment: Dick Heederik, Utrecht University |
| 10 - 11 am | One Health risk assessment at its best: source attribution of zoonotic infections: Lapo Mughini Gras, RIVM |
| 1 - 2 pm | The role of animals in the transition towards a sustainable and circular food system: theory: Evelien de Olde, Wageningen University |
| 2 - 3 pm | The role of animals in the transition towards a sustainable and circular food system: practice: Evelien de Olde, Wageningen University |

Friday 28th August Topic Chair: Joke van der Giessen, Wim van der Poel

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|----------------|---|
| 9 - 10 am | Wildlife and Public Health: Joke van der Giessen, RIVM |
| 10 - 11 am | The challenge of reducing public health risk from wildlife: Mirriam Maas, RIVM |
| 1 - 2 pm | Healthy and resilient livestock: Annemarie Rebel, Wageningen University |
| 2 - 3 pm | Sustainable Animal Production/ Livestock resilience: Ingrid van Dixhoorn, Wageningen Livestock Research |
| 3.30 - 4.30 pm | Wrap up |